

Maqam Sidi bil Hasan ash-Shadhili

By Barhoumi Romdhane, Institut Supérieur Islamique

Entry tags: Sufi, Tomb, Mysticism, North Africa, Tunisia, Islamic Traditions, Sufism, Sunni, Religious Place, Religious Group, Sufi Order, Sacred Territory, Sacred mountain

Le sanctuaire le plus célèbre de l'ordre Shadhili en Tunisie. Il représente un sanctuaire pour l'élite et le grand public, en particulier pendant les fêtes religieuses. Pendant le moi de Ramadan, les nuits sont consacrées à la prière, au dhikr et à la rencontre des familles.

Date Range: 1815 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Tunis Jallaz

Region tags: Africa, Northern Africa, Tunisia, North Africa, Tunisia

Le sanctuaire est situé dans l'ancien cimetière de Tunis, qui est le cimetière de Jellaz. Au sommet de la montagne appelée colline du Jellaz. Sur la route vers le sud de la Tunisie

Status of Participants:

Elite Religious Specialists Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

— Elevation

- Type of elevation
 - Hill
 - Mountain
 - Other [specify]: يوجد المقام في أعلى هضبة "الجلاز"

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

— Yes

- A single structure
 - Yes
 - The structure has a definite shape
 - Other [specify]: Le bâtiment est rectangulaire, mais il se compose de trois parties : la mosquée, le mausolée et la grotte
- One single feature
 - Mound
- A group of structures:
 - No
- A group of features:
 - Yes
 - Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No
 - Notes: Le bâtiment comporte trois parties : la mosquée, la grotte et le mausolée

- Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - No

- What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
 - Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Worship

↳ Worship:
– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

↳ In antiquity
– Periodically

Notes: كان المقام يحتوي على مغارة للخلوة ومسجد صغير كان يلتقي فيه أبو الحسن الشاذلي بتلاميذه أنشئ في القرن الثالث عشر

↳ In modernity
– Renaissance

Notes: في القرن 19 قام الوزير مصطفى خزندار بتشييد بناية فخمة

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Les gens croient que Sidi Belhassen El-Shazly a de nombreux honneurs et pouvoirs spirituels qu'il confère à ses compagnons.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: 2020، عبيد، هشام، وبن عامر، توفيق، نشأة الطريقة الشاذلية بإفريقية، دار نقوش عربيّة،
- Source 2: عبيد، هشام، تونس وأولياؤها الصالحون في مدوّنة المناقب الصوفيّة، مركز النشر الجامعي، تونس، 2006. الرابط: http://www.credif.org.tn/PORT/doc/SYRACUSE/2279/%D8%AA%D9%88%D9%86%D8%B3-%D9%88%D8%A7%D9%88%D9%84%D9%84%D9%8A%D8%A7%D9%88%D9%87%D8%A7-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B5%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AD%D9%88%D9%86-%D9%81%D9%8A-%D9%85%D8%AF%D9%88%D9%86%D8%A9-%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D9%86%D8%A7%D9%82%D8%A8-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B5%D9%88%D9%81%D9%8A%D8%A9-%D9%87%D8%B4%D8%A7%D9%85-%D8%B9%D8%A8%D9%8A%D8%AF?_lg=fr-FR
- Source 3: ابن الصباغ محمد بن أبي قاسم، كتاب درة الأسرار وتحفة الأبرار في مناقب سيدي أبي الحسن الشاذلي، المطبعة التونسية الرسمية، 1973
- Reference: 1989، بوذينة، محمد. أبو الحسن الشاذلي. تونس: دار التركي للنشر،
- Source 1: الحشاينبي، محمد بن عثمان. الدرّ الثمين في التعريف بأبي الحسن الشاذلي وأصحابه الأربعة. تونس: المطبعة الرسمية العربيّة، 191
- Source 2: 1988، محمود عبد الحلیم، قضية التصوف: المدرسة الشاذلية، دار المعارف، مصر،

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:
Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.
– Yes

↳ Type of feature
– Mound

- Terracing
- Trackway or road-surface
- Water feature
- Plantings
- Other [specify]: يوجد المكان في أعلى مكان يشرف على مقبرة الجزار

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

- No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eMxVh3l-BMI>
- Source 1 Description: Une courte vidéo sur la Hadhra de Sidi bilHasan Shadhuli
- Source 2 URL: <https://books.google.tn/books?id=OCfVIH46B5cC&pg=PA11&dq=%D9%85%D9%82%D8%A7%D9%85+%D8%B3%D9%8A%D8%AF%D9%8A+%D8%A8%D9%84%D8%AD%D8%B3>
- Source 3 URL: http://www.mawsouaa.tn/wiki/%D8%A3%D8%A8%D9%88_%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AD%D8%B3%D9%86_%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B4%D8%A7%D9%86
- Source 3 Description: Une biographie du marabout Sidi bilHasan Shadhuli

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

- Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

- Yes

↳ Body present:

- No

Reference: الحشايشي , محمد بن عثمان . الدّرّ الثمين في التعريف بأبي الحسن الشاذلي وأصحابه الأربعة . تونس : المطبعة الرسميّة العربيّة , 1910

↳ Part of body present:

- No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

- Yes

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

- Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

- Yes

Notes: la colline est entouré d'un réseau de routes séparant la ville de Tunis au banlieue sud

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

- Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

- No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

- Yes

↳ Specify

- King or emperor
- Private individual
- Other [specify]: Le sanctuaire était une maison de prière bien connue, mais il a été démolé 42 fois, puis le cheikh Abi al-Hasan al-Shadili l'a renouvelé. En 1867, le ministre Mustafa Khazindar a construit de luxueux bâtiments surplombant la ville de Tunis.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

- Men
- Women
- Specialized labourers/craftspeople
- Other [specify]: Les murids de l'ordre Shadhili ont aidé à construire le bâtiment

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

Specify

- Revealed by other kind of supernatural being(s) [specify]: Dans la grotte à côté de la mosquée, il a rencontré le Prophète Musa, la paix soit sur lui, et sayidna Al-Khidr, et l'endroit a acquis une force spirituelle

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Specify

- Other [specify]: Avant la construction de la mosquée, Abu al-Hasan al-Shazli résidait dans la grotte, et il a été dit qu'il avait rencontré le Prophète al-Khidr, et il y avait beaucoup de partisans, alors il a renouvelé la petite mosquée.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Reference: الأندلسي, أبي عبدالله محمد بن محمد. الحلل السندسيّة في الأخبار التونسيّة. تونس: دار الكتب الشرفيّة, 1871 مطبعة الدولة التونسيّة بتونس 1970.

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– No

Notes: Le ministre Mustafa Khaznadar a décidé, en guise d'expiation pour le péché d'avoir volé l'argent de l'État tunisien, de construire le sanctuaire, un immense bâtiment, avec un gros prêt financier

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Other [specify]: المقام كان بيت صلاة مشهور بالفضل واستجابة الدعاء لاعتقادهم أن من يقبض فيه 14 ليلة يرى سيدنا الخضر وتجاب دعوته

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: 2020. عبيد، هشام، وبن عامر، توفيق، نشأة الطريقة الشاذلية بإفريقية، دار نقوش عربيّة،
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– Source 3 URL: http://www.mawsouaa.tn/wiki/%D8%A3%D8%A8%D9%88_%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AD%D8%B3%D9%86_%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B4%D8%A7

– Source 3 Description: Une biographie du marabout Sidi bilHasan Shadhuli

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

– Mountain

– Other [specify]: يوجد المقام في أعلى هضبة "الجلاز"

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

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Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Other [specify]: Le bâtiment est rectangulaire, mais il se compose de trois parties : la mosquée, le mausolée et la grotte

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↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

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↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: Le bâtiment comporte trois parties : la mosquée, la grotte et le mausolée

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

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↳ Worship:

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↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

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Notes: في القرن 19 قام الوزير مصطفى خزندار بتشييد بناء فخمة

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Les gens croient que Sidi Belhassen El-Shazly a de nombreux honneurs et pouvoirs spirituels qu'il confère à ses compagnons.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

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Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

↳ Body present:

– No

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↳ Part of body present:

– No

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↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

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Notes: Le ministre Mustafa Khaznadar a décidé, en guise d'expiation pour le péché d'avoir volé l'argent de l'État tunisien, de construire le sanctuaire, un immense bâtiment, avec un gros prêt financier

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Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: عُلِّقَت الجدران الداخليَّة للمسجد بالجليز المزركش بالأشكال الهندسيَّة والنباتيَّة

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Il y a des cadres entourant les murs entiers de la mosquée sur lesquels sont écrits les noms des étudiants de Sidi Belhassen à la manière Shadhili, entrecoupés de grands cadres de cristal dans lesquels sont écrits certaines des supplications et des poèmes de Sidi Belhassen, qui sont appelés "Hizb" et parmi les plus célèbres d'entre eux sont « Hezb Al-Bahr » et « Hezb Al-Lat ».

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Voire ci-dessous

Notes: Il y a des inscriptions décoratives en plâtre sur lesquelles certaines des supplications du célèbre cheikh ont été écrites et un texte écrit indiquant le sanctuaire. Le dôme était entouré d'inscriptions d'art marocain, sur lesquelles le nom du cheikh était écrit sur sa ceinture.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: كتب على اللوحات المتحركة أسماء التلاميذ الأربعة لابي الحسن الشاذلي كابي الحسن علي الخطّاب، وحزب و حسن السيجومي ... و ايضا أدعيته وأدكار مشهورة كحزب "اللطيف" و حزب "الفلاح" وحزب "الدائرة" و حزب "التوسّل"

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–Secco

–Other [specify]: كتبت على محيط القبة التي تتوسط المسجد أسماء الله الحسنى 99 باللون الأزرق

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: دهن سقف المسجد المنقوش من الخشب والإطارات الخارجيّة للنوافذ الحديدية باللون الأخضر الذي يدلّ على لون الجنة

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: النقوش الموجودة لأسماء الله الحسنى وكذلك اسم سيدي بلحسن وتلاميذه للتبرك

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: La cour avant est séparée de la mosquée par trois arches constituées de mats de marbre surmontés d'un arc de marbre noir et blanc. Quant au dôme extérieur, elle est couverte de tuiles vertes, se terminant par des briques Al_qarmid de cuivre inégales avec un croissant symboliste l'Islam.

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Dans le bâtiment il y a une ancienne grotte où un moine chrétien nommé Adil avait l'habitude de vénérer. Le roi de Carthagène avait l'habitude de lui demander sa bénédiction et de lui rendre visite deux fois par an, et après cent ans mon maître Belhassan y résida avec ses compagnons.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

- ↳ Earth
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Sand
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Clay
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Plaster
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Wood
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Grass
 - No
- ↳ Stone
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Glaçure et marbre pour le carrelage et fer pour la décoration des balcons et des fenêtres

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: En premier lieu, le carrelage a été utilisé pour recouvrir le mur d'un type d'émail décoré andalou et marocain, en plus de portes en bois et de grandes fenêtres donnant sur des balcons avec des barrières en fer de caractère hafsi.

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Dans le bâtiment il y a une ancienne grotte où un moine chrétien nommé Adil avait l'habitude de vénérer. Le roi de Carthagène avait l'habitude de lui demander sa bénédiction et de lui rendre visite deux fois par an, et après cent ans mon maître Belhassan y résida avec ses compagnons.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Plaster
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Wood
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Grass
 - No
- ↳ Stone
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Glaçure et marbre pour le carrelage et fer pour la décoration des balcons et des fenêtres

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: En premier lieu, le carrelage a été utilisé pour recouvrir le mur d'un type d'email décoré andalou et marocain, en plus de portes en bois et de grandes fenêtres donnant sur des balcons avec des barrières en fer de caractère hafsi.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

- ↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
 - Yes

- ↳ On the outside:
 - No

- ↳ On the inside:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
 - Yes

- ↳ Is the decoration figural:
A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted
– No
- ↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
– Yes
- ↳ Is it geometric/abstract
– Yes
- ↳ Floral motifs
– Yes
Notes: عُلفت الجدران الداخليّة للمسجد بالحليز المزركش بالأشكال الهندسيّة والنباتيّة
- ↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
– Yes
Notes: Il y a des cadres entourant les murs entiers de la mosquée sur lesquels sont écrits les noms des étudiants de Sidi Belhassen à la manière Shadhili, entrecoupés de grands cadres de cristal dans lesquels sont écrits certaines des supplications et des poèmes de Sidi Belhassen, qui sont appelés "Hizb" et parmi les plus célèbres d'entre eux sont « Hezb Al-Bahr » et « Hezb Al-Lat ».
- ↳ Other [Specify]
– Other [specify]: Voire ci-dessous
Notes: Il y a des inscriptions décoratives en plâtre sur lesquelles certaines des supplications du célèbre cheikh ont été écrites et un texte écrit indiquant le sanctuaire. Le dôme était entouré d'inscriptions d'art marocain, sur lesquelles le nom du cheikh était écrit sur sa ceinture.
- ↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
– Yes
- ↳ Can the decoration be revealed:
– Yes
- ↳ Are there statues present:
– No
- ↳ Are there reliefs present:
A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.
– No
- ↳ Are there paintings present:
– Yes
- ↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:
– Yes
Notes: كتب على اللوحات المتحركة أسماء التلاميذ الأربعين لابي الحسن الشاذلي كآبي الحسن علي " و حزب الخطاب و حسن السجومي ... و ايضا أدعيته وأذكار مشهورة كحزب " اللطيف " و حزب " الفلاح " و حزب " الدائرة " و حزب " لتوسل "
- ↳ Are they wall paintings:
– Yes
- ↳ Type
– Secco
– Other [specify]: كُتبت على محيط القبة التي تتوسط المسجد أسماء الله الحسنى 99 باللون الأزرق

- ↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:
 - No
- ↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:
 - No
- ↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
 - No
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: دهن سقف المسجد المنقوش من الخشب والإطارات الخارجيّة للنوافذ الحديدية باللون الأخضر الذي يدلّ على لون الجنة
- ↳ Are there mosaics present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: النقوش الموجودة لأسماء الله الحسنى وكذلك اسم سيدي بلحسن وتلاميذه للتبرّك
- ↳ Other type of decoration:
 - Yes [specify]: La cour avant est séparée de la mosquée par trois arches constituées de mats de marbre surmontés d'un arc de marbre noir et blanc. Quant au dôme extérieur, elle est couverte de tuiles vertes, se terminant par des briques AL_qarmid de cuivre inégales avec un croissant symbolisant l'Islam.

Iconography

- Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
 - No

Beliefs and Practices

- Is supernatural monitoring present:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
 - Notes: يطالب في "الحضرة" بقراءة المدايح و أدعية تعرف بأحزاب سيدي بلحسن الشاذلي مثل حزب اللطيف وحزب الدائرة وحزب الشكوى وحزب التوشل

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:
– I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:
– Yes
- ↳ Other:
– Other [specify]: الحضرة التي تقام في المقام هي عملية تطهير روحيّة من الرذائل الأخلاقيّة ليقترّب الانسان من الله تعالى وينقل دعاءه ويجيب طلبه

Are pilgrimages present:
– No

Is divination present:
– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:
– No
Notes: دفن أبو الحسن الشاذلي في ضريح في حمشيرة في صحراء عيذاب بصعيد مصر جنوب البحر الأحمر عندما رجع من الحج

Do rituals occur at this place:
Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.
– Yes

- ↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– Yes
- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– No
- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
– specify: أكثر من 500 زائر
- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: تقام الحضرة 14 ليلة من كلّ خميسن في شهر رجب وقد يمكنون يم الجمعة والسبت
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– No
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– No
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– Yes
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:
– Yes

- ↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

–Yes [specify]: تقدم حراف أو دبكة أو دجاج ويطبخ لروّار الحضرة أو سعطى للفقراء

↳ Are there human sacrifices:
– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:
– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– No

↳ Are they sky deity:
– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– Yes
Notes: Sidi Belhassan a plusieurs dignités, dont la guérison des malades

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– Yes

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– Yes

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– Yes
Notes: تمنح بركات للشفاء من الأمراض البدنيّة والنفسيّة وقضاء الحوائج كتيسير الزواج وإجاب الأطفال و تحقيق الثروة وإطعام الجياح والفقراء

↳ Are they other:
– Other [specify]: في وقت الأزمات في الدولة التونسيّة كالحروب كان الفقراء و الجياح يقصدون المقام لمساعدتهم

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– Yes

Notes: Certains fidèles en présence peuvent accomplir des actes surnaturels tels que l'insertion d'un couteau dans une partie du corps ou la marche sur des charbons ardents sans être blessés s'ils atteignent un état d'extase.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: يعبد أصحاب الطريقة الشاذليّة الله تعالى ومن خلال الحضرة وحلقات الذكر والتعليم يتّجهون إلى الله الواحد

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: من خلال الدعاء والذكر وطلب تحقيق الأمنيات

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: قد يخاطب المریدون سيدي بلحسن الشاذلي ليقبل طلباتهم

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– No

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: أغلب الحاضرين في الإحتفالات هم من أصحاب الطريقة الشاذليّة

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: يقام الذكر في بيت الصلاة أمّا الحضرة فتكون في الشّاحة الأماميّة لانساعها

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– No

- ↳ Cleansing
 - Yes
- ↳ Offerings of models of body parts:
 - No
- ↳ Expiation
 - Yes
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: بعض الزوّار يكونون من المرضى ويقع شفاؤهم أثناء احتفالات الحضرة وقد يصاب بعض الحضور بالإغماء بعد القيام بالرقص

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - Yes
 - Notes: En présence, le murid peut voir son cheikh, Sidi Belhassan al-Shazli, et il peut aussi voir al-Khidr, que la paix soit sur lui, et cela est attesté par ce que mon maître Belhassan a dit à ses étudiants : "Quiconque passe 14 nuit dans le Maqam le vendredi soir ne meurt pas avant d'avoir vu al-Khidr, que la paix soit sur lui." Il a également dit: "Le fidèle djinn visite mon sanctuaire le vendredi soir."
- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - I don't know
 - Yes
 - Notes: أنظر كتاب محمد بوزينة ، أبو الحسن الشاذلي ، دار التركي للنشر ، 1989 ، صفحة 91

Are festivals present:

– Yes

- ↳ Frequency of festivals
 - specify: إضافة لليللي الذكر والحضرة ، تقام احتفالات في شهر رمضان و في الأعياد الدينيّة
- ↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):
 - All members
 - Elites
 - Non-elites
 - Other [specify in comments]
 - Notes: كلّ الحاضرين من أتباع الطريقة الشّاذليّة
- ↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Requires new construction/decoration of the place:
 - Yes
 - Notes: تفرش الزرابي في الساحة أو داخل بيت الضّلاة لاستقبال الوافدين
 - ↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):
 - No
- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
 - number: أكثر من 500
 - Notes: يصل عدد الحاضرين في مقام سيدي بلحسن الشاذلي بمصر في منطقة حميترة بصعيد مصر حيث يوجد قبره إلى مليون زائر

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:
– No

Are material offerings present:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: هذه الهيات تعطى لتزيين المقام أو ليستخدمها الزوار كالمفروشات للمبيت أو المأكولات

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:
– Yes

↳ By all the community
– No

↳ By specific individuals
– Yes [specify]: المنتمين للطريقة الصوفية الشاذلية

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: إن حلفة الذكر والدعاء و المدائح النبوية في "الحضرة" تعطى لأصحاب الطريقة الصوفية الشاذلية
قوة روحانية تمكّنهم من رؤية كثير من الأشياء

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:
– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:
– Yes

↳ Significant value:
Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value
– Yes

Notes: Ces choses sont de rechercher des bénédictions, la guérison, la subsistance et de faciliter le mariage et la procréation

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:
– Yes

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: Les visiteurs offrent des sacrifices d'animaux, tels que des moutons, des poulets, des coqs et des denrées alimentaires à distribuer à "Al-Zarda" ou à "Al-Hadara", qui a lieu tous les jeudis des 14 semaines du mois de Rajab, pour le souvenir, la supplication et les louanges du Messager, que Dieu le bénisse et lui accorde la paix.

↳ Other
–Yes [specify]: Ils fournissent également des lustres, des tapis et des meubles précieux pour le sanctuaire

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:
– Yes
Notes: يمكن أن يحضر في " الحصرة " الجان المؤمن كما قال سيدي بلحسن لتلاميذه

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:
– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:
– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):
– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
– Yes
Notes: كان المقام يحتوي على مغارة و مسجد ر و ساحة صغيرة إلى أن شيد الوزيرمصطفى خزندار في 1867 بناءات فخمة

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: أعمال صيانة و تنظيف المقام يتمّ بها القائم بشؤون الزاوية بمساعدة عملة

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: عادة ما يكون من أصحاب الطريقة الصوفية الشاذلية

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: عادة ما يكون المشرفون على تسيير "الحضرة" من مریدی الطريقة الصوفية الشاذلية

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: دفن أبو الحسن الشاذلي في ضريح في حميرة في صحراء عيذاب بصعيد مصر جنوب البحر الأحمر عندما رجع من الحج

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

Notes: Ces choses sont de rechercher des bénédictions, la guérison, la subsistance et de faciliter le mariage et la procréation

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Les visiteurs offrent des sacrifices d'animaux, tels que des moutons, des poulets, des coqs et des denrées alimentaires à distribuer à "Al-Zarda" ou à "Al-Hadara", qui a lieu tous les jeudis des 14 semaines du mois de Rajab, pour le souvenir, la supplication et les louanges du Messenger, que Dieu le bénisse et lui accorde la paix.

↳ Other

–Yes [specify]: Ils fournissent également des lustres, des tapis et des meubles précieux pour le sanctuaire

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Sidi Belhassan a plusieurs dignités, dont la guérison des malades

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Yes

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: تمنح بركات للشفاء من الأمراض البدنية والنفسية وقضاء الحوائج كنسب الزواج وإنجاب الأطفال و تحقيق الثروة وإطعام الجوع والفقراء

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: في وقت الأزمات في الدولة التونسية كالحروب كان الفقراء و الخياج يقصدون المقام لمساعدتهم

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Certains fidèles en présence peuvent accomplir des actes surnaturels tels que l'insertion d'un couteau dans une partie du corps ou la marche sur des charbons ardents sans être blessés s'ils atteignent un état d'extase.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: يعبد أصحاب الطريقة الشاذلية الله تعالى ومن خلال الحضرة وحلفاء الذكر والتعليم يتجهون إلى الله الواحد

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: En présence, le murid peut voir son cheikh, Sidi Belhassan al-Shazli, et il peut aussi voir al-Khidr, que la paix soit sur lui, et cela est attesté par ce que mon maître Belhassan a dit à ses étudiants: "Quiconque passe 14 nuit dans le Maqam le vendredi soir ne meurt pas avant d'avoir vu al-Khidr, que la paix soit sur lui." Il a également dit: "Le fidèle djinn visite mon sanctuaire le vendredi soir."

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

– Yes

Notes: أنظر كتاب محمد بوزينة ، أبو الحسن الشاذلي ، دار التركي للنشر ، 1989 ، صفحة 91

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: إن حلقة الذكر والدعاء و المدائح النبوية في "الحضرة" تعطى لأصحاب الطريقة الصوفية الشاذلية: قوة روحانية تمكنهم من رؤية كثير من الأشياء

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: يمكن أن يحضر في " الحضرة " الجان المؤمن كما قال سيدي بلحسن لتلاميذه

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: عادة ما يكون من أصحاب الطريقة الصوفية الشاذلية

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: عادة ما يكون المشرفون على تفسير "الحضرة" من مردي الطريقة الصوفية الشاذلية

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:
– Yes
Notes: يطالب في "الحضرة" بقراءة المدايح و أدعية تعرف بأحزاب سيدي بلحسن الشاذلي مثل حزب اللطيف وحزب الدائرة وحزب الشكوى وحزب التوشل

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:
– Yes

↳ Other:
– Other [specify]: الحضرة التي تقام في المقام هي عملية تطهير روحيّة من الرذائل الأخلاقيّة لينتقرب الانسان من الله تعالى ويقبل دعاءه ويحب طلبه

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:
– Yes
Notes: من خلال الدعاء والذكر وطلب تحقيق الأمنيات

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:
– Yes
Notes: قد يخاطب المریدون سيدي بلحسن الشاذلي ليقبل طلباتهم

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– No

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
– specify: أكثر من 500 زائر

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

تقام الحضرة 14 ليلة من كل خميس في شهر رجب وقد يمكثون يوم الجمعة والسيب: specify-

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
- No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
- No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
- Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
- No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:
- Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:
- Yes [specify]: تقدم خراف أو ديكه أو دجاج ويطبخ لزوار الحضرة أو سعطى للفقراء

↳ Are there human sacrifices:
- No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:
- No

Are there self-sacrifices present:
- No

Are material offerings present:
- Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
- No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
- Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
- Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
- No

↳ Other
- Other [specify]: هذه الهيات تعطى لتزيين المقام أو ليستخدمها الزوار كالمفروضات للمبيت أو المأكولات

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:
- Yes

↳ By all the community
- No

↳ By specific individuals
- Yes [specify]: المنتمين للطريقة الصوفيّة الشاذليّة

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: كان المقام يحتوي على مغارة و مسجد ر و ساحة صغيرة إلى أن شيد الوزير مصطفى خزندار في 1867 بناءً فحمة

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: أعمال صيانة و تنظيف المقام يتم بها القائم بشؤون الزاوية بمساعدة عملة:

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– No

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: أغلب الحاضرين في الإحتفالات هم من أصحاب الطريقة الشاذليّة:

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

–Yes [specify]: يقام الذكر في بيت الصلاة أمّا الحضرة فتكون في الشاحة الأماميّة لتسعها:

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

–specify: إضافة لليللي الذكر والحضرة ، تقام احتفالات في شهر رمضان و في الأعياد الدينيّة:

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

–All members

–Elites

–Non-elites

–Other [specify in comments]

Notes: كلّ الحاضرين من أتباع الطريقة الشاذليّة

Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– Yes

Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

Notes: تفرش الزرابي في الساحة أو داخل بيت الصلاة لاستقبال الوافدين

Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– No

On average, how many participants gather at this place:

–number: 500 أكثر من

Notes: يصل عدد الحاضرين في مقام سيدي بلحسن الشاذلي بمصر في منطقة حميثة بصعيد مصر حيث يوجد قبره إلى مليون زائر

Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

Incubation

– No

Healing magic

– No

Cleansing

– Yes

Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

Expiation

– Yes

Other

–Other [specify]: بعض الزوّار يكونون من المرضى ويقع شفاؤهم أثناء احتفالات الحضرة وقد يصاب بعض الحضور بالإغماء بعد القيام بالرقص

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

Notes: يكونون عادة من مريدي الطريقة الشاذلية

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Notes: في وقت الأزمات كالحروب أو المجاعة كانت الزاوية تقدّم إعانات للفقراء و تطعم المحتاجين

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

Notes: Dans le passé, près de la grotte, dans le sanctuaire, il y avait une source courante appelée "elhammem". Il n'en reste aujourd'hui aucune trace à l'exception du réservoir d'eau. Les gens recherchaient les bénédictions de son eau.

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: هو مكان فيه طاقة روحية

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

Notes: توجد أذكار ومدائح و أدعية لسيدي بلحسن تعرف بالأحزاب مكتوبة في إطارات بلُوريَّة متحركة على كلِّ جدران بيت الصَّلَاة

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: يرّدها المریدون شفويًّا في حلقات الذكر:

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

Notes: كانت المغارة الموجودة في المقام قبل 100 سنة لراهب مسيحي يتعمّد بها ثمّ اتّخذها ابو الحسن الشاذلي خلوة للعبادة

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

Notes: يوجد في تجويف القبة في بيت الصَّلَاة نقش فيه أسماء الله الحسنی

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: هناك إطارات بلوريَّة كتب فيها أسماء تلاميذ أبي الحسن الشاذلي توجد على محيط جدران بيت الصَّلَاة

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: قد يكون لمقّدم الزاوية الذي يشرف عليها بيت أو غرفة خاصة

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– No

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: تهتمّ وزارة الشؤون الدينيّة و المعهد الوطني لحماية التراث بالمقام

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

Notes: يكونون عادة من مردي الطريقة الشاذليّة

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: قد يكون لمقدم الزاوية الذي يشرف عليها بيت أو غرفة خاصة

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: تهتم وزارة الشؤون الدينيّة و المعهد الوطني لحماية التراث بالمقام

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– No

- ↳ Does this place lease out tools:
– No

Public Works

- Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:
– Yes

- ↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:
– Yes
Notes: في وقت الأزمات كالحروب أو المجاعة كانت الزاوية تقدّم إغانات للفقراء و تطعم المحتاجين

- ↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
– No

- ↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Function for water management:
– Yes
Notes: Dans le passé, près de la grotte, dans le sanctuaire, il y avait une source courante appelée "elhammem". Il n'en reste aujourd'hui aucune trace à l'exception du réservoir d'eau. Les gens recherchaient les bénédictions de son eau.

- ↳ Part of the transportation network:
– No

- ↳ Other
– Other [specify]: هو مكان فيه طاقة روحية

Writing/Scriptures

- Is non-religious writing stored at this place:
Economic documents, records etc.
– No

- Are there scriptures associated with this place:
– Yes

- ↳ Are they written:
– Yes

- ↳ Are they written at this place:
– Yes
Notes: توجد أدكار ومدائح و أدعية لسيدى بلحسن تعرف بالأحزاب مكتوبة في إطارات بلورة متحركة على كل جدران بيت الصلاة

- ↳ Are they oral:
– Yes
Notes: يرثدها المریدون شفويًا في حلقات الذكر

- ↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:
– Yes
Notes: كانت المغارة الموجودة في المقام قبل 100 سنة لراهب مسيحي يتخذ بها تمّ أخذها ابو الحسن الشاذلي حلوة للعبادة

- ↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:
– No

- ↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

Notes: يوجد في تجويف القبة في بيت الصلاة نقش فيه أسماء الله الحسنى

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: هناك إشارات بلورية كتب فيها أسماء تلاميذ أبي الحسن الشاذلي توجد على محيط جدران بيت الصلاة

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